

**STUDIES OF DELAMINATION GROWTH AND
FINAL FAILURE UNDER TENSILE LOADING**

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ABSTRACT

Experiments were performed to investigate the mechanisms of delamination initiation, growth, and subsequent final failure. Specimens laminated from both Hercules AS4/3501-6 unidirectional graphite/epoxy tape and Hercules A370-5H/3501-6 woven graphite/epoxy fabric were tested to isolate the influence of interlaminar normal stress (σ_{zz}) and thermally-induced interlaminar stresses on delamination initiation. The data was successfully correlated using the Quadratic Delamination Criterion and indicated that thermally-induced interlaminar stresses can cause delamination initiation without the application of mechanical load. Graphite/epoxy specimens in a $[0_{n+15}]_s$ ($n = 1$ to 5) configuration and in a $[\pm 15]_3$ configuration (specimen widths 10 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, 50 mm, and 70 mm) were used to evaluate the effects of effective ply thickness and specimen width on delamination growth and final failure. These specimens were loaded beyond delamination initiation in increments of up to 25 MPa until final failure. Delaminated area was determined via dye penetrant-enhanced x-radiography. The results showed that growth of sufficient size to be detected by the x-radiography is delayed until the onset of transverse cracking in the angled plies. These cracks always occur at the tips of the edge delamination. The delamination front then advances with the tip of the transverse crack and extends between the tip of the crack and the free edge. This emphasizes the importance of the interaction of in-plane and out-of-plane damage modes leading to final failure. A thickness effect on growth and final failure similar to that seen for delamination initiation in earlier work was observed. There was no specimen width dependence of the stress at which significant stable growth first appeared or of the final failure stress.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is an important failure mode in advanced composite laminates. It manifests itself in both laboratory specimens and actual structures. For example, it is believed that out-of-plane stresses prompted the failure of the composite vertical fin for the L-1011 in the NASA ACEE program [1]. This type of problem has made it necessary to consider delamination in order to provide a damage tolerant design [2].

Delamination by itself cannot cause final failure under tensile

loading. In-plane fracture must occur for the specimen to lose its load carrying capability. Thus, it is a question of how delamination interacts with in-plane failure modes (e.g. transverse cracking, fiber fracture) to cause final failure. The process of failure via delamination can therefore be broken down into three stages: initiation, growth and interaction with in-plane modes, and final failure.

Two approaches for predicting and correlating delamination initiation currently exist: the strain energy release rate approach [e.g. 3] and the strength of materials approach [e.g. 4,5]. The strain energy release rate approach is based on the fracture mechanics concept that sufficient strain energy must be available to create the new surface area at initiation. The strength of materials approach is based on the concept that a strength parameter must be exceeded at initiation. The former methodology has been extended to growth whereas the latter has not. No attempts have been made to predict final failure as prompted by delamination.

In this work, aspects of all three stages of tensile delamination failure of graphite/epoxy specimens are investigated.

SCOPE AND APPROACH

The work has been divided into two segments: delamination initiation, and growth and final failure.

Delamination Initiation

The strength of materials approach for predicting delamination initiation has been demonstrated via the Quadratic Delamination Criterion [6]:

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{1z}}{Z^{s1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{2z}}{Z^{s2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{[\bar{\sigma}_{zz}]}{Z^t}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ is the average of stress component σ_{ij} over a given averaging dimension x_{avg} from the free edge:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{1}{x_{avg}} \int_0^{x_{avg}} \sigma_{ij} dx \quad (2)$$

Z^{s1} , Z^{s2} , and Z^t , are the interlaminar strengths for stress components σ_{1z} , σ_{2z} , and σ_{zz} , respectively, and the brackets indicate that only tensile values of σ_{zz} are considered. The data in Reference 6 support the applicability of the Quadratic Delamination Criterion to specimens in which delamination initiation is controlled by the interlaminar shear stress σ_{1z} . Evidence is needed for its applicability to specimens in which delamination initiation is governed by the interlaminar normal stress σ_{zz} .

Calculation of the interlaminar stresses at the free edges σ_{zz} of laminates was accomplished using the technique developed by Kassapoglou and Lagace [7]. In this technique, expressions for the interlaminar stress distributions are assumed in terms of constant and exponential terms. The expressions are based on properties that the interlaminar stress distributions must have in order to assure integral force and moment equilibrium. The exponential parameters are determined by minimizing the laminate complementary energy and the boundary conditions and traction continuity between plies are satisfied exactly. These calculations indicate that laminates in a cross-ply configuration (i.e. only 0° and 90° plies) isolate the effects of the interlaminar normal stress as the

interlaminar shear stresses are either identically zero (σ_{1z}) or negligible (σ_{2z}). However, cross-ply laminates will exhibit transverse cracking in the 90° plies at low applied stresses. This alters the three-dimensional stress field near the free edge and does not isolate delamination initiation from other damage modes.

In order to prevent transverse cracking, laminates with Hercules AS4/3501-6 unidirectional graphite/epoxy tape and A370-5H/3501-6 graphite/epoxy fabric were used in these three configurations: $[0_5/0_f]_s$, $[0_5/0_f/0]_s$, and $[0_{10}/0_f]_s$. The subscript "f" denotes a fabric ply. Five specimens of each laminate type were used. These laminates are cross-ply configurations since the fill fibers in the fabric are at a 90° orientation. Nonetheless, the construction of the fabric inhibits transverse cracking in these plies. The effect of the interlaminar normal stress on delamination initiation is thus isolated in these laminates. The calculation of the interlaminar stresses is simplified for the special case of cross-ply laminates and can be calculated with a closed form version [8] of the methodology of Kassapoglou and Lagace. The three dimensional elastic constants for the two materials used in the calculations are listed in Table 1. In this table, the subscripts "1" and "2" are the in-plane directions and "z" is the out-of-plane direction.

Growth and Final Failure

The second segment of the work investigated delamination growth, interaction with in-plane failure modes, and final failure. In these experiments, $[0_{\pm 15}]_s$ specimens made of Hercules AS1/3501-6 graphite/epoxy and $[\pm 15_2]_s$ specimens of varying widths constructed from Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy were used. Both of these laminate configurations are known to delaminate before final failure [6] when constructed of AS1/3501-6 graphite/epoxy.

TABLE 1
Material Properties of Hercules A370-5H/3501-6 and
Hercules AS4/3501-6 Graphite/Epoxy Composites

	A370-5H/3501-6	AS4/3501-6
t_{ply}	0.35 mm	0.134 mm
E_{11}	72.5 GPa	142 GPa
E_{22}	72.6 GPa	9.8 GPa
E_{zz}	10 GPa	9.8 GPa
G_{12}	4.4 GPa	6 GPa
G_{1z}	4.4 GPa	6 GPa
G_{2z}	4.4 GPa	4.8 GPa
ν_{12}	0.059	0.30
ν_{1z}	0.30	0.30
ν_{2z}	0.30	0.34

In the $[0_n/\pm 15_3]_s$ laminates, the normalized effective ply thickness, n , varied from one to five. Five specimens of each effective ply thickness were investigated. Interlaminar stress calculations show that the interlaminar stress components are proportional to the applied far field stress and are functions of distance from the free edge normalized by ply thickness. Thus, laminates with greater effective ply thicknesses have larger regions of high interlaminar stresses and are subject to delamination at lower applied stresses [9]. It is therefore important to investigate the effects of effective ply thickness on delamination growth and final failure.

In the case of the $[\pm 15_3]_s$ specimens, five different specimen widths were used: 10 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, 50 mm, and 70 mm. Five specimens of each width were tested. These different widths were used to determine the effect of specimen width on delamination growth and final failure, specifically to determine whether a critical amount or percentage of test section area needs to delaminate in order to trigger in-plane failure mechanisms.

THE EXPERIMENT

Specimen Characteristics

Although different fiber types and configurations were used in this investigation, all material systems used contained 3501-6 epoxy as the matrix and were cured in two stages with a one hour "flow" stage at 116°C and a two hour "set" stage at 177°C. The cure took place in an autoclave under 0.59 MPa pressure and full vacuum. All specimens were 350 mm long straight-edged coupons and were cut from laminated plates using a water-cooled diamond-grit cutting wheel. Glass/epoxy loading tabs were bonded onto each specimen in a secondary operation with American Cyanamid FM-123-2 film adhesive. The ratio of nominal tab thickness to nominal laminate thickness was always in the range of 1.5 to 4 as recommended [10]. The tabs were 75 mm long with a 30° bevel at the test section. The test section was therefore 200 mm long. With the exception of the $[\pm 15_3]_s$ specimens, the nominal width of all specimens was 50 mm. A strain gage was mounted in the center of the test section of each specimen. The test specimen configuration is shown in Figure 1.

The free edges of the delamination initiation specimens were carefully

Figure 1. Test specimen characteristics.

polished in order to increase the clarity of edge replications. Polishing was done with a 25 mm felt bob mounted in a drill press. The felt bob was continually dipped in a colloidal solution of a fine abrasive, Kaopolite SF, which has an average particle size of 0.7 microns. A smooth back and forth motion was used while the free edge was pressed against the felt bob.

Damage Evaluation Techniques

In the delamination initiation experiments, the testing machine was stopped under computer control immediately when it was determined that the applied load had dropped from the previous data point. This load drop under stroke control can be indicative of loss in modulus in the delaminated region [3]. The sensitivity to such load drops is dependent on the size of the initiation, the reduction in modulus in the delaminated region, the frequency of the data acquisition, the resolution of the load measurement, and the noise in the data acquisition system. The data acquisition rate was selected in order to minimize the chances of missing the load drops which accompany delamination initiation while also reducing the number of tests inadvertently stopped by noise in the data acquisition system [11].

Delamination initiation was confirmed using an edge replication technique. After each test, the stroke was reduced by a factor of two and an edge replication was made. Acetate tape was softened with acetone and then smoothed against the specimen edge. When examined under a microscope at magnifications of 5X to 20X, delamination initiations could be detected. These were compared to replications from the previous test or replications made before any tests were run. If no initiation was found, the load drop was assumed to have been caused by noise in the data acquisition system and the specimen was retested. If initiation was found, the stress at the load drop was taken to be the initiation stress. The edge replication technique is described in detail in Reference 11.

In the second segment of work, delaminated area was determined via dye penetrant-enhanced x-radiography. The computer stopped each test at a predetermined load level. The load increments were usually based on a 25 MPa stress increase on the specimen's nominal dimensions. Smaller increments were used once damage was detected in a specimen of the same type. After the specimen reached its maximum load for a given test, the stroke was reduced by a factor of two, the free edge swabbed with diiodobutane (DIB), and the specimen removed from the testing machine and x-rayed.

Testing Procedures

All specimens were tested under computer control in a Material Test System MTS 810 testing machine equipped with hydraulic grips. A stroke rate of 1.1 mm/minute yielded a strain rate of approximately 5000 microstrain/minute in the test section. Load, strain, and stroke data were recorded automatically every 0.3 seconds through a data acquisition system. The specimens in the first segment of the work were "load drop tested" until initiation was found. In the second set of experiments, delaminated area was monitored as a function of stress level.

RESULTS

Delamination Initiation

The $[0_{10}/0_f]_s$ specimens were not tested as they all exhibited delamination initiation at the specimen midplane on the edge replications taken before any load was applied. This result implies that interlaminar stresses resulting from curing stresses are responsible for delamination initiation in these cases and must be taken into consideration. These

Figure 2. Thermally-induced interlaminar normal stress versus distance from the free edge in $[0_{10}/0_f]_s$ laminate.

thermally-induced interlaminar stresses were included in the average stress components calculated for the Quadratic Delamination Criterion. The interlaminar stresses resulting from thermal effects were determined using the same basic method as for mechanical stresses. Energy terms, however, were redefined for the thermally-induced loading case as detailed in Reference 12. The distribution of the thermally-induced interlaminar normal stress for the $[0_{10}/0_f]_s$ laminate is shown in Figure 2. In these cases, the temperature differential used is -156°C , the difference between the cure temperature (177°C) and room temperature (21°C).

Of the five $[0_5/0_f]_s$ and five $[0_5/0_f/0]_s$ specimens, only three $[0_5/0_f]_s$ specimens yielded valid delamination initiation stresses. Edge replications showed delamination initiations at the midplane. The seven remaining specimens all had one test after which no delamination initiation was detected followed by a test which was stopped after damage visible to the naked eye occurred but no load drop had stopped the test. Edge replications confirmed that delamination initiations had occurred at the midplane in the $[0_5/0_f]_s$ specimens and at the $0_f/0^\circ$ interface in the $[0_5/0_f/0]_s$ specimens. The load drops that accompanied the delamination initiations were most likely so small that they could not be detected by the data acquisition system. This results from the extremely small change in modulus when these laminates delaminate. The initiation stress of these seven specimens can only be narrowed to a range. For the two $[0_5/0_f]_s$ specimens which did not yield delamination initiation stresses, the average of the stress levels for the last test which showed no delamination initiations was 520 MPa while the average delamination initiation stress of the other three $[0_5/0_f]_s$ specimens was 528 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 2.6%. This implies that 528 MPa is a good value for the delamination initiation stress of the $[0_5/0_f]_s$ specimens. The range of stresses in which delamination initiation occurred in the $[0_5/0_f/0]_s$ specimens is 451 MPa (with a coefficient of variation of 6.5%) to 744 MPa (with a coefficient of variation of 3.9%).

In Table 2, actual delamination initiation stresses are compared with predictions using the Quadratic Delamination Criterion in which thermally-induced effects are included. Predictions were made using an averaging dimension of 0.178 mm as found for Hercules AS1/3501-6 laminates [6] and an interlaminar normal strength of 43 MPa as found by direct experiment for Hercules AS4/3501-6 [13]. It was found that the contribution of the interlaminar shear stress σ_{2z} in these cases was

TABLE 2
 Predicted versus Actual Initiation Stress and
 Average Interlaminar Normal Stress at Initiation

Laminate	Predicted Initiation Stress ^a [MPa]	Actual Initiation Stress [MPa]	Average Interlaminar Normal Stress at Initiation [MPa]
$[0_5/0_f]_s$	436	528	44.6
$[0_5/0_f/0]_s$	681	451-744	39.4-44.0
$[0_{10}/0_f]_s$	0	0	43.4

^a Averaging dimension is 0.178 mm (thermally-induced stresses are included).

negligible. Delamination initiations all occurred at the interfaces predicted using the Quadratic Delamination Criterion. Values of the average interlaminar normal stress, $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$, at the experimentally measured delamination initiation stresses were also calculated using Equation (2) and are also shown in Table 2. As the thermally-induced stresses dominate in these laminates, moderate variations in applied mechanical load do not significantly affect the value of $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$. This allows the laminate delamination initiation stress to be quite sensitive to the actual interlaminar normal strength.

Growth and Final Failure

The delaminated area of the $[0_{\pm 15}]_s$ specimens was monitored as a function of stress level. Previous work [6] with $[0_{\pm 15}]_s$ specimens showed that delamination initiation virtually always occurred prior to the initiation of transverse cracks. However, transverse cracks did subsequently initiate in all cases and were followed by the simultaneous growth of the transverse crack and the delaminated region. In all cases, the transverse crack formed at the intersection of the delamination tip and the free edge. The delaminated region usually took the shape of a triangle between the free edge and a transverse crack in the +15° ply. It should be noted that the growth did achieve temporary stability when the delamination and the transverse crack stopped in the interior of the test section as shown in the x-ray and schematic drawing in Figure 3. The area of the delaminated region could be approximated as half the product of the length of the delamination along the free edge and the "intrusion", the perpendicular distance from the free edge to the innermost part of the delamination as illustrated in Figure 3. Since the transverse crack is always at a 15° angle to the free edge, the ratio of the length of the transverse crack to the intrusion is the cosine of 15°.

An "average first growth stress range" was defined for each specimen type as the range of stresses bounded by the average maximum stress at which there was no delaminated area detectable via x-radiography and by the average stress at which a delaminated area was first detectable. The maximum delaminated area and intrusion detected before failure were also recorded. The average quantities for each specimen type are given in Table 3.

In general, delamination growth and failure occurred at lower stress levels for the thicker laminates. It should be noted that only the five specimens with n equal to one actually broke into two pieces. The

Figure 3. X-ray photograph (left) and schematic drawing (right) of typical delaminated area in $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_S$ specimens.

remaining $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_S$ specimens suffered massive splitting of all plies, delamination at the $0^\circ/+15^\circ$ and $+15^\circ/-15^\circ$ interfaces, and severe loss of stiffness at "failure". The delamination always started at the $+15^\circ/-15^\circ$ interface, as has been predicted and observed for delamination initiation in this laminate [6]. Only after some additional growth did delaminations occasionally "jump" across a transverse crack to the $0^\circ/+15^\circ$ interface. After this growth was observed, some transverse cracking of the -15° plies in the delaminated region could be observed. The phenomenon of delaminations jumping to other interfaces has been observed previously [e.g. 14]. Once delamination growth began, failure occurred relatively quickly as there were usually only one to three load increments from the detection of first growth until final failure. Maximum intrusion

TABLE 3
Delamination Growth Data for $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_S$ Specimens

Effective Ply Thickness n	Average First Growth Stress Range [MPa]	Average Failure Stress [MPa]	Maximum Intrusion Before Failure [mm]	Delaminated Area Before Failure [cm ²]
1	1091-1129	1212	4	1
2	812-849	884	23	15
3	722-747	772	22	32
4	639-671	777	26	23
5	633-660	714	22	22

Figure 4. Typical plot of maximum intrusion of delaminated area versus stress level and strain energy release rate for $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_s$ specimens (Note: strain energy release rate scale is quadratic).

is shown as a function of stress level and strain energy release rate for a typical $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_s$ specimen in Figure 4. The strain energy release rate is calculated using the simplified equation of O'Brien [3]:

$$G = \frac{\epsilon^2 t}{2} (E_{\text{lam}} - E^*) \quad (3)$$

where G is the total strain energy release rate, ϵ is the strain level, t is the laminate thickness, E_{lam} is the modulus of the laminate, and E^* is the modulus in the delaminated region as determined by the rule of mixtures approach. This yields an R-curve type plot.

TABLE 4
Delamination Growth Data for $[\pm 15_3]_s$ Specimens
With Different Widths

Width [mm]	Average First Growth Stress Range [MPa]	Average Failure Stress [MPa]	Maximum Intrusion Before Failure [mm]	Delaminated Area Before Failure [cm ²]
10	492-497	497	0	0
20	487-502	502	0	0
30	496-505	509	3	2
50	474-482	505	8	2
70	478-483	488	31	22

In previous work with similar (AS1/3501-6) $[\pm 15_3]_S$ specimens, delamination initiation always occurred before the initiation of transverse cracks. No evidence could be detected that such was not the case for the AS4/3501-6 specimens in this work. The transverse crack and the delaminated region in the specimens in this work grew simultaneously in the manner depicted in Figure 3. The average values of first growth stress range, maximum intrusion and delaminated area before failure, and failure stress are tabulated for the different width $[\pm 15_3]_S$ specimens in Table 4. It can be seen that the failure stresses for the various widths are the same within experimental scatter, but delaminated area does increase with width. All of the 10 mm wide specimens, four of the five 20 mm wide specimens, and three of the five 30 mm wide specimens broke into two pieces at failure. The remaining $[\pm 15_3]_S$ specimens did not break into two pieces, although significant portions of the $+15^\circ$ surface plies did "peel" from the surface.

DISCUSSION

The results of tests with the specimens with both fabric and unidirectional plies show that thermally-induced interlaminar stresses and the interlaminar normal stress can be important in causing delamination initiation. The bounding of the interlaminar normal strength was quite close to the value found for AS4/3501-6 by direct tests in Reference 13.

The fact that moderate variations in the applied far-field stress cause small changes in the value of average interlaminar normal stress results from the relatively large contribution of the thermally-induced interlaminar normal stress. For example, thermally-induced interlaminar normal stress accounts for 79% of the total average interlaminar normal stress at delamination initiation of the $[0_5/0_f]_S$ specimens. The thermally-induced and mechanically-induced components of the interlaminar normal stress as well as their total can be seen for the $[0_5/0_f]_S$ laminate in Figure 5.

It is important to note that the strain energy release rate approach as applied by O'Brien [3] and represented in Equation (3) would not predict the delamination initiation at the midplane that was seen in the $[0_5/0_f]_S$ and $[0_{10}/0_f]_S$ specimens because the simple rule of mixtures formula for determining the decrease in modulus would show no loss in stiffness and therefore no energy available for creating a new delaminated surface. In

Figure 5. Total, as well as components of, interlaminar normal stress versus distance from free edge in $[0_5/0_f]_S$ laminate at delamination initiation stress.

fact, this energy is available through B-matrix (bending-stretching coupling) terms which become important when the laminate separates into two unsymmetric halves [15]. These terms are neglected in the simple rule of mixtures approach.

The $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_s$ specimens and the $[\pm 15_3]_s$ specimens with different widths exhibited delaminated areas bounded on one side by a transverse crack which grew in relatively small stress ranges. This implies that a favorable interlaminar stress state and a transverse crack in the $+15^\circ$ ply are both necessary for a delamination to grow significantly. The interaction of the in-plane (transverse cracking) and out-of-plane (delamination) damage modes eventually triggers final failure. The growth apparently proceeds in somewhat stable bursts. It is possible however that stable growth occurs over stress ranges smaller than those used in these experiments and thus were not detected herein.

The $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_s$ specimens exhibited a decrease in strength with increasing thickness. This is the same trend as was found for delamination initiation [6]. Since initiation and growth must occur before failure, it is not surprising that the laminates which initiated earlier also failed earlier.

In the 10 mm and 20 mm wide specimens, the first burst of delamination growth was large enough to grow completely across the specimen and trigger final failure. In the wider specimens, some growth could be accommodated without unstable growth and final failure. Nonetheless, the stress level needed to cause unstable growth of delamination and transverse cracking and the subsequent final failure is not a function of specimen width. The failure stresses observed are near the initiation stress of 508 MPa found for AS1/3501-6 $[\pm 15_3]_s$ laminates in previous work [6]. It should be noted that, in wider specimens, the transverse cracks can run a longer distance before failure and thus a greater portion of the test section length can delaminate.

CONCLUSIONS

The set of experiments with the specimens containing fabric and unidirectional plies supports the use of the Quadratic Delamination Criterion for predicting delamination initiation. The data indicates that this criterion is applicable when initiation is dominated by the interlaminar normal stress. The results further show the importance of including thermally-induced interlaminar stresses in the average stress calculations.

The results of the tests of the $[0_n/\pm 15_n]_s$ specimens and the $[\pm 15_3]_s$ specimens with different widths show that delamination growth and failure are dependent on the thickness of the laminate (as are the delamination initiation stress and the interlaminar stress field itself) but not on the specimen width. It appears that significant delamination growth requires not only delamination initiation but also the subsequent initiation of a transverse crack. The delaminated area then extends between the transverse crack and the free edge. This emphasizes the importance of the interaction of in-plane and out-of-plane damage modes in delamination growth and final failure.

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